

**EXAMINATION OF ARCTIC LAND USE AND
BIODIVERSITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES:
LINKS BETWEEN LOCAL LIVELIHOODS, ALBEDO,
AND CLIMATE**

CHARTER deliverable 6.3

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Project Duration: 54 months

Project Officer: Alberto Zocchi

Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

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Contributing partners: LAY, UmU, UHAM

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Authors: Hans Tømmervik and Jarle W. Bjerke (NINA), Jussi T. Eronen (UH), Sirpa Rasmus (LAY), Joachim Otto Habeck and Kirill Istomin (UHAM), Tim Horstkotte (UmU)

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1 Introduction

Reindeer (*Rangifer tarandus*) globally utilizes vast mountain heaths, forests, taiga and tundra as grazing land. While large population fluctuations are characteristic in wild reindeer herds such fluctuations in herded populations may pose major challenges to the economy and livelihood of indigenous herder communities or local herder communities (Tømmervik et al. 2012; Stark et al. 2023). Additionally, climatic change, diseases and new land uses may inflict with the reindeer husbandry (Riseth et al. 2020; Laptander et al. 2023). Reindeer may influence the albedo of lichen dominated vegetation communities (Aaartsma et al. 2020). Also moose (*Alces alces*), often found in the same areas as reindeer/caribou, increase the forest albedo relatively to un-browsed forests by grazing and browsing, which in turn driving biophysical cooling (Salisbury et al. 2023).

Large herbivores are important in shaping the structure and functioning of terrestrial plant communities (Côté et al. 2004; Ramirez et al. 2018). The density of herbivores mediates the strength at which they directly and/or indirectly interact with vegetation (Olf and Ritchie 1998). Biodiversity is positively influenced by large herbivores like reindeer, and Ramirez et al. (2024) analyzed the role herbivory has on plant richness and diversity. Vegetation diversity and richness did not present any differences between treatments (fenced or open plots), yet reindeer had an increasing effect on herbaceous plant diversity. Herb abundance was negatively related to shrubs in both treatments but with a faster decline in the absence of herbivores, suggesting that herbivory increases plant diversity by reducing shrub abundance (Ramirez et al. (2024). Moderate grazing of lichen areas may increase the diversity of mosses and lichens and reduce abundance of shrubs and dwarf shrubs (Andrejev 1977; Tømmervik et al. 2012, 2021).

The focus of this report is how Arctic land use and management of biodiversity and land-surface albedo can support resilience of local communities and Arctic ecosystems. We aim to empirically examine how the Arctic land use and biodiversity management can support climate change adaptation and how climate change mitigation actions can increase resilience of Arctic local communities and livelihoods. This entails an assessment of how the use of reindeer pastures with biodiversity increase can be achieved considering that perturbation of the different functional groups increases the total biodiversity (Ramirez et al. 2024; in addition, lichen, moss, etc. are important components of biodiversity). However, disequilibrium or imbalance might occur either when the vegetation is too slow to respond to a perturbation, or if it lags behind an environmental change caused by a change in the climate or continued human activity (Bürgi et al. 2017; Tømmervik et al 2019).

In this report, we discuss the resilience of reindeer herding using the social-ecological system (SES) framework (Folke et al. 2016). The land-use and biodiversity management practices are important building blocks of the herding community resilience, as they directly link to present day and future pasture resources and economics, and play a role in climate change adaptation and mitigation. For more holistic consideration, also socio-cultural aspects of resilience need to be discussed.

We have divided this report into sections: first we present new research concerning pasture management focusing on albedo, and then we discuss the economic and socio-cultural aspects related to resilience. Finally, we discuss the sustainability and resilience of reindeer herding communities, concentrating on the landcover – albedo linkages. We emphasize the impact that lichens, shrubs, and grazing on these, can have on land-cover albedo (both during snowless and snow-cover seasons, Figure 1), and through this, on regional climate. Please see earlier CHARTER deliverables, concentrating on observed land-cover changes (D1.3: Report on pan-Arctic biodiversity change on decadal scale; D2.1: Synthesis on the effect of grazing and trampling on plant biodiversity at a circumpolar level, and D2.2: Expected habitat-specific vegetation trajectories under differing grazing management practices, land-use histories and environmental conditions). Regarding the socio-economic aspects, we also refer to WP3 deliverables.

Figure 1. Contrasts in surface albedo and vegetation driven by differing rangeland grazing regimes, with contrasting effects between summer and winter.

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Social-ecological systems (SES) and resilience elements

We studied several cases of **social-ecological systems (SESs)** around the CHARTER region (Fennoscandia and northwest Russia), with emphasis on Norway. We used a combination of original research during the CHARTER project with recently published studies from the study region. Comparative case studies from West-Finmark and Fæmund/Røros are based on new material.

Resilience can be defined as the capacity of a system to absorb and cope with disturbances while maintaining its key structures and functions; capacity to reorganise while undergoing change (Folke, 2006; Folke et al., 2010; Furberg et al., 2011). Sarkki et al. (2016) have reformulated this to be more relevant to reindeer husbandry livelihood: the ability to renew and maintain the viability of the livelihood in the face of external and internal pressures, and the capability to positively adapt by reorganizing the functions of herding and by having influence on governance. Resilience is a property of the livelihood; adaptation means concrete actions by herders or others. Successful adaptation to changes maintains and enhances resilience (Lépy et al. 2018). Cultural resilience has been defined as the ability to maintain livelihoods that satisfy both material and moral needs in the face of major stresses and shocks (Crane 2010). Transmission of practitioner knowledge is considered to be an important element in the cultural resilience, as well as traditions, languages, value systems and everyday practices and doing (Furberg et al. 2011; Oskal et al. 2009). Resilient livelihoods are characterized by positive renewal and cultural continuity (Lépy et al. 2018).

We consider resilience encompassing elements like economy, climate change adaptation and mitigation, ecological state, and social and cultural viability. In reindeer husbandry SESs, humans and their biophysical environment are closely linked, and the potential for climate change adaptation and mitigation is linked to cultural and social aspects in the communities in question.

Cases and scales

The cases and scales discussed in this report are illustrated on the Map 1. From Norway the cases are Fæmund reindeer herding district (RHD) in Røros, West Finnmark (Kautokeino), as well as wild reindeer ranges in southern Norway. From Sweden, we discuss the Könkämä sameby. Cases from Northwest Russia come from Yamal and Komi.

From Finland, we present three typical cases – material that can be generalized within certain types of districts – but giving also examples from actual districts. We follow the categorization used in CHARTER Deliverable D2.2 – here herding districts in Finland were categorized depending on the presence of forests and the intensity of forestry (Stark

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et al. 2024) – and combine it to regional categorization of districts within the reindeer management area (RMA). Districts within the categories have commonalities in pasture environment and pressures of other land-uses, and in herding practices and cultures, as well. Consequently, the seasonality of reindeer grazing, and pasture rotation possibilities and practices vary between the categories (Helle & Jaakkola 2008; Holand et al. 2023). Districts in Finland comprise:

- (1) herding districts with larger proportion of nature conservation areas, old growth forests and less intensive forestry
- (2) herding districts with intensive forestry, and consequently young forest age distribution
- (3) fell districts mostly located in subarctic climate vegetation zone.

Northern case: The 13 northernmost herding districts form the Sámi Homeland area (SHA) in Finland. Most of these belong to category 3 (fell districts). Näkkälä and Käsivarsi herding districts are two examples of these districts. Here some pastures are specifically utilized as summer pastures, but most are used year-round. The seasonal pasture use and pasture rotation are nevertheless guided by active herding. Within districts that are located in SHA, decision making related to pasture use and practical work happens in practice at the level of siida (family group/kinship), and reindeer owned by herders from certain siida graze certain pasture areas within the district. In these northern districts the size of reindeer herds is typically larger and herding is the main source of livelihood for a larger proportion of herders, compared to the central and southern parts of the area, where herds are generally smaller and it is common to practice herding as a part-time job.

Mid-region case: South from the SHA southern border, eight more districts belong to the “area specially intended for reindeer husbandry”. Both category 1 and category 2 districts are found from this region. Muonio and Kyrö (category 2), and Lappi and Kemin-Sompio (category 1) are examples from this region. There is variability in herding practices within the region. Supplementary winter feeding is practiced more in some districts, less in some others. Some have clear pasture rotation (differentiation to summer and winter pastures, fences), and reserve pastures for extremely difficult winters, examples of these are Lappi, Kyrö and Kemin-Sompio (Rasmus et al. 2023). Muonio is an example of districts where some pastures are declared as summer pastures, but most are used year-round (Lépy et al. 2018). There is nevertheless an aim to develop the seasonal pasture rotation.

Southern case: Most herding districts further south feature more intensive forestry (meaning they come under category 2) and multiple other land-use types like agriculture, mining, settlements, wind energy production and so on. Taivalkoski, Näljänkä and Oivanki are examples of these districts. In many districts (especially in small districts in southern part of the RMA), pasture rotation exists but is very small-scale: movement of animals within sub-regions of the district, between pasture lands and biotypes according to the annual cycle of reindeer life and pasture vegetation. Grazing of reindeer is guided by work groups or village groups of herders within these sub-regions. In these districts other land

use has led to significant decrease of usable seasonal pastures, and especially the impact of forestry has been long-term (Helle & Jaakkola 2008). Because of this, more intensive winter feeding and keeping reindeer in winter enclosures for feeding are more common practices in the central and southern parts of the RMA than in the Sámi Homeland area where herding is generally practiced on natural pastures (Turunen & Vuojala-Magga 2014). In southern and mid-part of the RMA, infrastructure and other land-use forms cover significant fraction of the land areas of the districts. This means that pasture rotation needs to be consolidated with multiple other land-uses of the region, and the planning of the pasture use is not in the herders' hands.

Map 1: CHARTER study region and cases discussed in this report. Design: Tim Horstkotte.

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2 Reindeer grazing and albedo

Albedo, the ratio of reflected to incoming solar radiation, is an important regulation factor on vegetation at high latitudes; thus, this has a profound impact on climate through complex interactions and feedback loops (Figure 1). Environmental changes driven by reindeer grazing affect the regulating ecosystem services (ESs) of vegetation. While lichens accumulate relatively little carbon compared to plants with which they compete for space, well managed reindeer lichen mats have a high albedo (Petzold and Rencz 1975; Bernier et al. 2011). Surface albedo is the ratio of incoming solar radiation reflected at surface level which is an essential physical attribute of the climate system (Finne et al. 2023). Thus, it is increasingly understood that it is important and necessary to include albedo as a climate-regulating service in climate impact assessment studies, particularly at high latitudes (Euskirchen et al. 2013). For example, snow and sea ice reflects c. 50-60 % of incoming solar radiation, thus the surface albedo feedback from declining sea ice is a primary driver of the Arctic amplification, as it allows more solar radiation to be absorbed by the darker surface of the ocean (Park et al. 2018). Lichen dominated tundra and boreal forests with a dense lichen cover on the ground have high albedos (Petzold and Rencz 1975), and reindeer herding thereby provides an important ecosystem service that potentially driving biophysical cooling and contributes curbing the effects of global warming (Finne et al. 2023; Bjerke et al. 2024).

Knowledge about how vegetation albedo varies along environmental gradients in tundra and boreal ecosystems is still lacking, particularly for ecosystems dominated by nonvascular vegetation as mosses and lichens (Finne et al. 2023). Different management systems and seasonal grazing affect the vegetation trends in complex ways, and the impact is in interaction with impacts of climate warming (Stark et al. 2023). Lichen cover has declined across northern Finland, but a recent slight recovery is seen in some areas. Lichens tolerate trampling badly, and lichen cover and height are on average lower in areas used for summer grazing than in those solely used for winter grazing (Tømmervik et al. 2012, Stark et al. 2024). Separating winter and summer pastures is recommended. But the intensity of forestry strongly impacts lichen as well, and the change in lichen cover has been higher in districts with intensive forestry (Kumpula et al. 2014; Stark et al. 2024). Data from Sweden suggests that both climatic conditions and grazing impact lichen cover. A slight general decrease in lichen cover is observed across the study area, with high small-scale variability. This was seen especially at sites with low reindeer density. In areas with high reindeer density, lichen cover showed increase at colder sites and decrease at warmer sites. Studies from Finnmark comparing the situation in 1998 and 2005 revealed a rapid increase in the lichen cover and lichen biomass with a reduction of the reindeer density with more than 50 % (Tømmervik et al. 2012).

2.1 Winter grazing areas

2.1.1 Northern Fennoscandia – Sápmi

Finne et al. (2023) studied broadband shortwave albedo of open boreal, arctic, and alpine ecosystems over a 2000 km long latitudinal gradient (60° N – 79° N) from South Norway to Svalbard and analyzed the albedo against species composition (biodiversity), vegetation greenness (normalised difference vegetation index NDVI), momentary ecosystem CO₂ fluxes, and domestic reindeer grazing pressure. The studies comprised both wild reindeer ranges (Finse on Hardangervidda and Svalbard) and domestic reindeer ranges (Fæmund RHD, Troms RHDs, and West-Finnmark RHDs).

High cover of pale terricolous fruticose lichens was the single most important predictor for vegetation albedo, which had a maximum value of 0.389 in Grådalen (Fæmund RHD) under clear sky conditions and solar zenith angle 60° (Figure 2). To our knowledge, this is the highest broadband albedo recorded for a vegetated surface ever. The high albedo due to large area of lichen dominated vegetation cover types in both districts led to biophysical cooling and curbing the effects of global warming.

Figure 2. Winter grazing of reindeer in lichen tundra gives a cleaner lichen surface which increase the albedo. The photo shows the site of Grådalen in Fæmund RHD (Røros). At this spot, the highest broadband albedo for a vegetated surface ever was measured in 2020.

The reason for this is that light to medium reindeer grazing impact benefits lichens because shrubs and grasses protruding the lichen mats are thinned or grazed down by reindeer (Lyftingsmo 1974; Andrejev 1977), hence increasing the albedo (Finne et al. 2023). The

average density of reindeer in Fæmund (Røros) is about the same as in West-Finmark, but the pasture management practices, including rotation of seasonal reindeer ranges, has resulted in a stable lichen biomass on the landscape level in Fæmund since the 1970s (Tømmervik et al. 2021). Even though wear by trampling and grazing may occur in the lichen mats (particularly on ridges), the rotational system enables rapid recovery and regrowth (Andrejev 1977; Tømmervik et al. 2012, 2021).

In an ungrazed lichen tundra (Figure 3) close to Fæmund RHD, albedo is lower due to protruding graminoids (grasses) like *Avenella flexuosa*, dwarf shrubs like bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus*) and crowberry (*Empetrum nigrum*) or shrubs like dwarf birch (*Betula nana*). Grasses and shrubs reduce the albedo and the lichen mat's ability to reflect sun radiation.

Figure 3. An ungrazed lichen mat in Sletthøe (Tolga near Røros) which is protruded by grasses like wavy hair-grass (*Avenella flexuosa*), dwarf birch (*Betula nana*), and the dwarf shrub crowberry (*Empetrum nigrum*), giving the landscape a light green shade combined with the grey lichen, hence lowering the albedo. Compared with Figure 2, the cover of more green plants on the top of the lichen mat is clearly visible.

While it is well-known that reindeer affects climate-relevant above-ground biomass of importance for reindeer (Kumpula et al. 2000; Tømmervik et al. 2012), we here show that its regulation of surface albedo in northern ecosystems may be of high importance for land-atmosphere interactions. This advocates for an increased understanding of the important

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and complex role of reindeer and lichen cover in climate-vegetation interactions. A cleaner and smoother lichen surface will probably reduce the plot-scale biodiversity of vascular plants, but not the landscape, since all vascular plants will still remain while the biodiversity of lichens may increase (Andrejev 1977; Molau & Alatalo 1998; Tømmervik et al. 2012; 2021).

2.1.2 Finland

In Finland, the “northern case” districts are very relevant to discussions on albedo. Already the remote-sensing study by Cohen et al. (2013) comparing winter and year-round reindeer grazing regimes along the Norwegian-Finnish border showed that grazing-induced vegetation changes resulted in differences in albedo dynamics there. Year-round pastures in Finland had shorter and sparser vegetation, resulting in delayed snowmelt, increased surface albedo, and decreased ground heating during the snowmelt season (May–June) compared to Norwegian pastures without grazing during the same period.

Based on pasture inventories, the change in lichen cover between the years 2008-2018 in Northern case has varied. In Käsivarsi it has decreased or remained unchanged, depending on the exact site. In parts of Näkkälä like the Palokorsa area the lichen cover is stable or increasing (Stark et al. 2024; Walenius et al. in review); hence albedo is higher here and might be comparable with parts of West-Finmark (Norway). The “mid-region” districts are not that relevant to albedo-related discussions, but of course reindeer grazing has a significant impact on forest ecosystems. Based on pasture inventories, the change in lichen cover between 2008 and 2018 in the mid-region case has varied. In Lappi it has decreased or remained unchanged, depending on the site; in Kyrö and Kemin-Sompio either decreased, increased or remained unchanged; and in Muonio decreased, significantly decreased or remained unchanged (Stark et al. 2024). It has been observed that lichen pastures are especially degraded in places where reindeer move and graze during snowless periods. GPS-tracking has shown that reindeer move to lichen pastures (for lichen, but for mushrooms also) already in early autumn, if there are no fences to separate the winter pasture areas. Also, the “southern case” districts are not that relevant to albedo-related discussions, and because of winter time herding practices keep reindeer away from lichen pastures most of the winter, the environmental impact of grazing is mostly restricted to snowless period. There is no information from the southernmost reindeer-herding districts about the change in lichen cover based on recent pasture inventories.

Lépy et al. 2018 have studied the community resilience at the Finland-Sweden border area, Könkämä-Muonionjoki River Valley, where Könkämä sameby (Sweden) and Käsivarsi herding district (Finland) neighbor each other across the border, as well as Muonio sameby (Sweden) and Muonio herding district (Finland). Seasonal pasture rotation is small-scale in Muonio herding district; herds migrate across the pine and spruce forests and peat lands

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of Muonionjoki River Valley; in Käsivarsi, different parts of the fell landscape are used by several siidas. Könkämä sameby comprises mountains, valleys, tundra and taiga environments with separate summer and winter pastures; summer pastures extend to Norwegian side. Muonio sameby has seasonal pastures in the boreal forests and wetlands. In this area, before the construction of fences along the nation-state borders, summer pastures of reindeer were near the Arctic Ocean, and winter pastures in boreal forests in the Muonionjoki River Valley (Pennanen and Näkkäljärvi, 2003). Now the pasture rotation in Finland is small scale and happens within rather small herding district borders – this threatens the lichen pasture quality through repeated utilization during winters, and possible trampling during summer.

In addition to examples above, material from Yamal-Nenets and Nenets regions has been published by Lavrinenko and Kuljugina (2002), Zhdanov (2009) and Beldiman et al. (2020).

2.2 Summer grazing areas; reindeer numbers, vegetation and albedo

Reindeer can control the growth of tall species like shrubs and trees through grazing, hence reindeer and other herbivores may mitigate a warming-induced reduction in plant diversity (Kaarlejärvi et al. 2015, 2017; Happonen et al. 2021). Such observations have been made in several places of northern Fennoscandia (Nordreisa, Kautokeino/West-Finnmark, Näkkälä etc.). This might increase albedo and therefore have a cooling effect on climate (te Beest et al. 2016). However, the strong effects of reindeer on albedo are probably restricted to areas with high reindeer densities, since a dramatic vegetation change is essential.

Reducing the reindeer numbers to enable lichen recovery would likely be echoed in mesic habitats where tall shrubs and forbs would increase, with negative consequences on vascular plant diversity as well as the quality of summer pastures for the reindeer. However, moss and lichen diversity may increase (Tømmervik et al. 2010, 2012) For example, a reduction in reindeer density in mid-Norway from 10 reindeer/km² to 2–3 reindeer/km² led to an increase of lichen abundance in dry areas, but at the same time also to increased shrubification, which reduced the proportion of good herb- and graminoid-rich summer pastures (Tømmervik et al. 2010). Thresholds that would prevent willows, dwarf birch, and mountain birch from invading tundra areas have been estimated to range between 3 and 5 reindeer per km² (den Herder et al. 2004; Tømmervik et al. 2010; Bråthen et al. 2017).

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Spiegel et al. (2023) concluded: “Where reindeer numbers varied over space, higher reindeer herbivory pressure was consistently linked with lower coverage of tall woody vegetation”. This is consistent with our results in Tømmervik et al. (2010) as well as in Bråthen et al. (2017) and den Herder et al. (2004). This means that that the density in Fennoscandia has to be more than 3–5 reindeer/km² during the summer period (90-120 days) to avoid shrubification. However, the density might be very high in Yamal (with a threshold of 21 reindeer/km²), but the sophisticated grazing system (that is, the loop-shaped design of herding-grazing movement) practiced in this region is crucial here, as described by Golovnev (2017): “For this purpose, the Yamal reindeer herders practice a “lacy design” of herd movement: after moving to a new camp, reindeer are put to graze on the next tundra along the sun around the camp in a radius of 5–7 km. After making 3–5 of such “loops” around the camp, the herder moves to a new place further ca. 7–10 km from the former.” This means that the real density of reindeer per km² in Yamal might equal to 3-5 reindeer/km² (for the whole summer season) found in Norway (see above). This is in agreement with the hypothesis in Spiegel et al. (2023): “Thus, we hypothesize that a lower density of Fennoscandian free-grazing reindeer without constant human control could exert greater pressure on vegetation, especially the preferred shrub pastures in June, by remaining longer in certain areas”.

3 Pasture use management, supporting climate change mitigation through increasing albedo

More than 50 years ago Robert Paine (1972), on the basis of his studies of Saami reindeer herding, concluded that there can be two principle types of grazing systems in nomadic pastoralism in general and reindeer herding in particular. The first aims at maximizing quality and quantity of grazing resources as well as quality of grazing conditions available for the herd at any given time. The second aims at distributing grazing load over the territory in order to ensure adequate grazing resources and conditions for the herd on a long-term basis. These two types lead to different systems of nomadic migration and different ways of maneuvering with the herd over pasturelands in those pastoralist systems where grazing under observation is practiced. Although from the modern point of view this conclusion can look rather simplistic (at the end of the day, any movement of the herd, including that guided by the herders in such a way as to maximize fodder available for the animals, represents a redistribution of grazing pressure as well), the two types identified by Paine can be usefully viewed as two poles of continuum between which various grazing systems, particularly those of nomadic pastoralists with intensive herding, are distributed. Thus, in the case of reindeer herding in Europe and Western Siberia, grazing systems that involve long linear migrations are closer to the maximizing pole. The main rationale behind such migrations is utilizing difference between types and seasonality of vegetation and/or grazing conditions (e.g. mosquito abundance) in different ecological zones and/or subzones

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in order to maximize the grazing resources available for the herd. In contrast, circular or loop-shaped migrations inside one ecological zone are mostly redistributing. The mostly maximizing grazing systems can be exemplified by those of the Nenets herders of central Yamal or those of Komi and Nenets systems of the eastern and central parts of Bolshezemelskaya tundra (North-east of the European part of Russia). These herders spend by far the largest part of the year travelling along an established migration path between its southernmost and the northernmost points and back, while the periods of staying in the northernmost point (summer pasturelands) and the southernmost point (winter pasturelands), when reindeer are pastured in the loop-like manner, are short (7 – 15 days and 1 – 2.5 months respectively). At the same time, the grazing systems of the northern Yamal, Southern Gydan, western part of the Bolshezemelskaya tundra as well as Malozemelskaya and Timan tundras are close to the redistribution pole: here no linear migrations are performed and reindeer are pastured in loop-like manner close to that described by Golovnev (2017) throughout the whole year. However, probably the most widely distributed systems of reindeer grazing are mixed ones. These systems include moving animals in a linear manner from winter to summer pasturelands and back. However, these linear migrations are fast and relatively short and the animals spend a significant if not the most part of the year on summer and winter pasturelands, where loop-like migrations take place. This system, as it seems, used to be practiced by many groups of Saami in Sweden and Norway (and it is still practiced by some) as well as by some groups of Khanty, Nenets and Komi in Western Siberia.

The effects of the grazing system on vegetation and particularly lichen cover is likely to differ, depending on the place of the system along the maximization/redistribution gradient. Thus, maximization systems seem to be quite rigid: the herders migrate along the same migration paths from year to year and even from generation to generation graze the same areas along these paths. This leads to long-term changes in vegetation. Thus in the north of the tundras of the north-east of European Russia, in areas outside protected territories, the amount of lichen is rather small (Uvarov et al. 2021), which is related to extensive grazing and trampling of reindeer that come here as a part of linear migration and go through the same area from year to year. The impact of this change of vegetation on the local reindeer herding is softened because the area is used in summer. The loop-like redistributing migrations, however, seem to be more flexible. The location of loops tends to change regularly, which has a positive effect on biodiversity.

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3.1 Winter grazing areas

A simple but very efficient measure to keep the lichen cover within winter grazing areas in good condition is to rotate the reindeer around in the winter grazing ranges (Stark et al. 2023), together with diminishing the detrimental impact by other land-uses like forestry that contribute to lichen decline (Kumpula et al. 2014; Sandström et al. 2016; Horstkotte and Moen 2019). Pasture rotation would here mean rotation between 'strict' summer- and winter ranges to prevent damage to lichens by trampling and grazing during summer (Stark et al. 2023). To further enhance the growth and the productivity in the winter grazing areas a winter rotation is set up in such a way that the same area is only grazed every third or fourth year giving a fresh and lush pasture every winter (Drake 1918, Vorren 1998, Stark et al. 2023). Using this type of management, the pastures will give a balanced and sufficient source of lichen to the reindeer maintaining forage, albedo, and biodiversity (Finne et al. 2023, Stark et al. 2023). Less supplementary or catastrophic feeding is needed in such a rotational system since there will be areas around in where the reindeer can find forage (Tømmervik et al. 2021). This will enhance the climate change adaption and mitigation, ecosystem state and social/cultural viability in reindeer herding since the large expenditure on supplementary feeding is not needed (Pekkarinen et al. 2015) as well as reduced risk for diseases (Tryland et al 2019; Riseth et al. 2020).

Unfortunately, winter rotation of pasturelands in reindeer herding is greatly hindered by unpredictability of grazing conditions as a function of the quality of snow cover. Environmental events such as rain-on-snow can and frequently do render large areas of winter pasturelands unusable in particular year, which leaves the herders little or no choice where to graze their animals. Even in years with limited ice crisp, however, snowfalls can render certain parts of winter pasturelands (for example those in river valleys or natural depressions) unusable due to the deep snow as winter progresses (for that reason Russian agricultural scientists advised herders to use winter territories near rivers and in narrow valleys first and switch to other patches later in winter (e.g. Друри and Митюшев 1963)). All this almost inevitably leads to the situation when certain patches of winter pasturelands, particularly those situated on elevations and in forest clearings where snow is slower to accumulate, are used more often than others. To make the thing worse, the quality of snow cover is likely to become even more unpredictable with the climate change. This does not mean that the winter pastureland rotation is impossible, of course. The problems outlined can be mitigated, for example, by reserving bigger territory for winter grazing.

Another important problem with winter grazing and pastureland rotation at least in the north-east of European Russia and in Western Siberia is related to the use of snowmobiles. In the last decades, snowmobiles became the main means of transportation reindeer herders use for winter herding operations: visiting and rounding up the herd,

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looking for stray animals, moving the herd from one area to another, etc. This, however, has led to abandoning pasturelands situated in the zone of dense forest, because snowmobiles cannot be used there, while reindeer herders do not want to switch back to skis in order to pasture there. Thus, reindeer herders of Izhemsky olenevod enterprise have abandoned about a half of their traditional winter area. Of course, this significantly decreases the rotation perspectives.

3.2 Summer grazing areas

Concerning strict summer grazing areas, Bråthen et al (2017) found that areas where reindeer densities were above a threshold of approximately 5 animals/km², they found, in accordance with the expectation of a “browse trap,” that the small life stages of shrubs in grasslands were at low height and low abundance and in danger of being removed/grazed down. Thresholds that would prevent willows, dwarf birch and mountain birch from invading tundra areas have been estimated to range between 3 and 4 reindeer per km² (den Herder et al., 2004; Tømmervik et al., 2010).

It seems to us that the use of redistributing design of grazing such as loop-shaped alone or in combination with the linear migration (e.g. as described in Golovnev 2017) can contribute to balancing the mean density in summer grazing areas. We recognize, however, that this combination can be possible only in some areas due to a complex of economic and even legal reasons. For example, in Bolshezemelskaya tundra, the whole territory is divided into long meridional “corridors” that belong to reindeer herding enterprises; these corridors are further divided into smaller strips of land belonging to individual nomadic camps (brigades). Each camp and each enterprise are supposed to graze inside its respective corridor and, in contrast to the Yamal Nenets Area this rule is rather strictly enforced: recently, there have been several court cases regarding the violation of the grazing territories and those found guilty were seriously fined (Истомин 2022). Since the corridors are very narrow, the use of loop-shaped herding in their northern part is hardly possible.

3.3 All-year around grazing areas

Reducing the reindeer numbers to enable lichen recovery would likely be echoed in mesic habitats where tall shrubs and forbs would increase, with negative consequences on diversity as well as the quality of summer pastures for the reindeer. This accounts for the all-around year pastures. For example, a reduction in reindeer density in mid-Norway from 10 reindeer/km² to 2–3 reindeer/km² led to an increase of lichen abundance in dry areas, but at the same time to increased cover of trees (forests) and shrubs which reduced

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the proportion of good herb- and graminoid-rich summer pastures (Tømmervik et al., 2010).

A special kind of all-year around grazing areas are grazing territories of nomadic camps that follow exclusively redistributing grazing models without linear migrations, e.g. the herders of the north of Yamal peninsula and of the southern part of Gydan peninsula (the Taz tundra). These herders migrate inside a restricted territory and usually make two or three loops during the year; while the camp stays in one location, the herd is pastured around it in the lace-like design. The exact geographic position of the loops changes from year to year. Although some areas inside the grazing territories are used exclusively in summer or in winter, most of the territory can be used in either season and, technically speaking, represents an all-year around grazing area. However, since several years can pass before certain patch of this area is used again in any season, the impact of grazing on vegetation is not very clear. Further research is definitely needed to relate the grazing pattern, seasonality of pastureland use and the impact of grazing on vegetation.

4 Economy as a resilience element

Reindeer density and pasture rotation practices have important effects on plant composition in Arctic and sub-arctic areas. Reindeer diet can vary, with a comparatively high intake of lichen in the snow-cover seasons *versus* a relatively high intake of leaves and buds of vascular plants in the snow-less seasons. These grazing patterns are decisive at micro- and meso-scale, determining the degree to which the landscape remains “open” or undergoes shrubification, the condition of lichen mats, and through both these dynamics, the degree of albedo. This has significance in global and regional economic terms.

4.1 Economic significance of albedo

While large population fluctuations are inherent in wild reindeer herds, such fluctuations in herded populations pose major challenges to the economy and livelihood of indigenous and local herder communities. Bjerke et al. (2024) analyzed the effect of such fluctuations in two winter herding areas (West-Finmark RHDs and Fæmund RHD) on core provisioning and regulating ecosystem. They compared 50-year long time series on herd size, meat production, forage productivity, carbon economy, and CO₂-equivalence metrics for surface albedo change based on the radiative forcing concept (Bright & Lund 2021; Bright et al. 2016). In 1973, albedo at district level was 6.9 % higher in West Finmark than in Fæmund. In 2018 (the last year with data from both districts), the

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albedo was 2.3 % higher in Fæmund than in West Finnmark. Albedo in Fæmund in 2020 was the same as in 1973. Reduction in albedo led to negative $\Sigma TDEE$ (= costs) in both districts, but to higher costs per unit area in West Finnmark than in Fæmund since the albedo was significantly lowered in West-Finnmark due to larger wear on the lichen mats there. However, comparison analysis showed that the economic benefits from the provisioning services for both reindeer winter districts were higher than the costs from the regulating services. Still, there were major differences; the district with stable reindeer density (8-10 reindeer/km²) gained nearly double on provisioning services per unit area than the district with larger and unstable fluctuations like varying density from 6-20 reindeer per km². Overall, the profit per km² was significantly higher in the winter district with the stable reindeer density (Fæmund). This study demonstrates that it is possible to minimize trade-offs between economic benefits from reindeer herding locally and global economic costs in terms of climate-regulating services (Bjerke et al. 2024). In addition, use of supplementary or catastrophic feeding is not used in the rotational system in Fæmund (Tømmervik et al. 2021).

Concerning summer grazing areas, the study by te Beest et. al. (2016) showed that summer grazing suppressing the growth of shrubs and forests, hence increase the local albedo and leading to a cooling effect in West-Finnmark/Troms. In order to assess the effects of reduction of albedo in summer grazing areas, de Wit et al. (2013) found that using future scenarios, forest cover in mountainous areas in Fennoscandia would increase from 12% to 27% between 2000 and 2100, resulting in a 59% increase in biomass carbon storage and an albedo change from 0.46 to 0.30. This reduction of albedo would lead to a warming 10 to 17 times stronger than the cooling effect from carbon sequestration for all emission metrics considered (de Wit et al. 2013).

43.2 Bioeconomic modelling

One way to estimate the economic aspects of reindeer herding is to use bioeconomic modelling (economic–ecological system models and economic optimization). The bioeconomic reindeer husbandry model (Tahvonen et al. 2014; Pekkarinen et al. 2015, 2017) can for example be used to estimate (economically) optimal slaughter strategies in different environmental conditions, for example when lichen biomass is lower or higher.

In Pekkarinen et al. 2023 three hypothetical herding districts (mountainous, mixed and forest herding districts) are described and modelled. This is needed because for example pasture conditions and migratory patterns and seasonal pasture uses differ greatly within northern Fennoscandia. Depending on prices and costs, different slaughter strategies become optimal. Lower lichen biomass is seen in these theoretical forest districts, because of a lack of pasture rotation (meaning grazing and trampling of lichen

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also during snow-free periods). On the other hand, arboreal lichen can be used (and it may be not economically beneficial to invest in higher lichen biomass, meaning in practice lower reindeer numbers). It may be optimal to use supplementary feeding as well. Of course, this depends for example on the price of the feed, and if different winter pastures are available or not.

Modelling can be used to estimate the impact of winters with difficult grazing conditions (Pekkarinen et al. 2022). Difficult winters decrease the net revenues of reindeer husbandry. However, they also protect lichen pastures from grazing, thus increasing net revenues in the future. Low lichen biomass appears to make reindeer management more sensitive to the effects of difficult winter conditions. It was found that it is economically sensible to use supplementary feeding during difficult winters. Also, predation and related compensations play a role in the decision making (Pekkarinen et al. 2020).

5 Resilience and social and cultural viability

This report focuses on pasture management in various cases, and how this links to seasonal land-surface albedo, and this way to regional climate, and to biodiversity. This enables discussing how Arctic land use exemplified by different reindeer herding strategies across Fennoscandia and Russia can support resilience of both local communities and Arctic ecosystems and climate. For more holistic understanding of SES resilience, also social and cultural aspects should be assessed. Here we give some examples and ideas to this end.

Expert opinions and local views on the status of different resilience elements (economic, social and cultural viability; climate change adaption and mitigation; ecological state) should be combined with monitoring data. The status of climate change adaptation can be estimated based on the possible and used adaptation measures; and elements of coping capacity (know-how, resources, options; knowledge base; governance support like compensations, subsidies, strategies to support the adaptation of the livelihood, guidance and education). One way to add social and cultural viability into the picture, a short list of Arctic Social Indicators, presented by Larsen et al. (2010), can be used:

1. Health/population (Infant Mortality; Net Migration)
2. Closeness to Nature (Consumption/harvest of local foods)
3. Material wellbeing (Per capita household income)
4. Education (Ratio of students successfully completing post-secondary education)
5. Cultural wellbeing (language retention, cultural autonomy, and belonging)
6. Fate Control (political control, percentage of local people in the governing body of the jurisdiction; economic control, % of public expenses from locally generated

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funds; cultural control, % of people speaking their “mother tongue”; control over land).

We consider especially numbers 5 and 6 as important, from social and cultural viability perspective. In cultural wellbeing, for example transmission of practitioner knowledge, traditions, languages, value systems and everyday practices and doing are significant.

For this kind of assessment, some material is easier to gather than other, and there are vast regional differences on the availability of material. There are more reports and statistics from Fennoscandian countries. But for example, when assessing the herding community resilience in the north-east of the European part of Russia and Western Siberia, infant mortality data is well available (Столяров 1993; Козлов et al. 2013; Климова, Ахметова, and Бобышев 2022; Быков, Талыкова, and Мегорский 2023), as well as data on migration (Vitebsky and Wolfe 2001; Liarskaia 2010; Povoroznyuk, Habeck, and Vaté 2010; Istomin 2022). Some material exists on house-hold income (Zuev 2020). and language retention (Вахтин 2001). Some other resilience elements need collecting expert opinions, analyses on political documents, and most importantly, co-producing knowledge with local herders – and this is the case in all regions where herding is practiced.

6 Conclusions and knowledge gaps

Reindeer density and pasture rotation practices have important effects on plant composition in Arctic and sub-arctic areas. Reindeer grazing patterns impact the land-surface albedo; reindeer provides an important ecosystem service that has potential to drive biophysical cooling and contribute to curbing the effects of global warming. We have presented cases from different countries and regions where different pasture management systems are in use, for various reasons – some internal for SESs described, some caused by external pressures and the state-level governance.

Resilience of a certain SES has various elements. We have emphasized here the ecosystem and climate related aspects. Locally speaking, it is a value-based decision, which resilience elements are emphasized most. It is important to acknowledge the multi-faceted nature of resilience, not forgetting the social and cultural aspects, neither downplaying the impacts pasture management can have on the environment, land-surface albedo and even regional climate. And that for example economy and the status of lichen pastures are tightly linked.

Is reindeer herding resilient in the communities described, thinking about its ability to mitigate climate change, and to adapt to changing climate and environment in sustainable

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ways? When thinking about the mitigation of climate change, it is important to maintain efficient enough summer grazing especially in fell environments under the risk of forest and tall shrub expansion (to keep the winter time albedo high), and at the same time prevent summer time trampling on lichen pastures (to make sure to keep the summer time albedo high, and to ensure the sufficient winter pasture resources also for the future).

For adaptation it is important to maintain flexible possibilities for locally acceptable and actionable adaptation measures (to climate change related changes, and also other changes), and generally strengthen the adaptive capacity of herders and communities. The elements of the capacity, needing strengthening, will depend on herder or community in question. Measures can vary from supplementary feeding to increased mobility, for example. All will need local planning and support from the governance, guidance, education and research of the livelihood. When planning the adaptation actions, it is important to think the sustainability of the measures – from ecological, economical and socio-cultural points of view. “Good” adaptation maintains or enhances the resilience, also to not-yet-experienced new pressures and events.

Herding is more than economic activity but is a livelihood in any case. It is important to maintain or enhance the economic viability and profitability.

The livelihood is changing all the time. It is expected that significant changes will be experienced during the following decades. Will the herding communities, SESs in question, be still able to maintain their key functions, and have influence on governance decisions? Will they be culturally resilient – will the livelihood continue to satisfy not only material but also moral needs? Will herders be able to transfer practitioner knowledge, traditions, languages, value systems and everyday practices and doing to future generations? Is there cultural continuity? Is it renewing in a positive way from herder point of view?

These questions are important for both future research, and also for the Arctic policy-making and local level planning.

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